
STUDY OF ROLE CONFLICT AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the role conflict and emotional intelligence among secondary school teachers. A sample of about 100 male and 100 female secondary school teachers were randomly selected from government and private school affiliated to PSEB board Amritsar district. Teacher's Role Conflict Inventory (Prasad & Bhushan; 1991) and Teacher's Emotional Intelligence Inventory (Mangal, 2008) were used for collecting the data. The findings of the study revealed that there exists no significant difference in role conflict and emotional intelligence of government and private secondary school teachers. However no relationship between role conflict and emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers was found

Keywords : Role Conflict, Emotional Intelligence and Secondary School Teachers.

INTRODUCTION

Education has fundamental role to play in personal and social development of the individual. It is the soul of human life and the process of acquiring knowledge. But in the teaching process teacher is the nuclear part of the total system. The role of the teacher will have to shape in the light of changing demands of the society. In fact, the teacher is the most significant feature in the learning environment provided by the institution. The entire range of human knowledge explodes in one time at an ever accelerating rate providing the best to its generation. This type of knowledge is being prescribed and transmitted from generation to generation by the teachers through the formal system of education. Teacher is expected to perform various roles as an organizer, a transmitter of necessary knowledge and skill, a demonstrator, a planner, an evaluator for the purpose of realizing educational goals. Better learning environment is a result of cooperation of teachers with other components of school and learning system. When teacher faces incompatible and contradictory expectations from different primary reference groups of the school as well as from different sections of society it interferes with the satisfactory performance of his role. Role conflict occurs when a person is expected to simultaneously act out multiple roles that carry contradictory expectations. When he perceives contradictory expectation, it gives rise to a situation called as role conflict. Such conflicting situations generate a struggle in the mind of teacher which is manifested either through aggressive behavior or withdrawal from reality. They may deviate from group norms and norms of teacher's behavior as well. Wu (2011) conducted a study in Taiwan, it was found that those suffering from role conflict also suffered greatly in their work performance, mainly in the form of lack of motivation. Gupta & Nain(2016) revealed that there is significant difference in role conflict and its dimensions among teachers working in govt./govt. aided and self-financing B.Ed. colleges. They suggested that there is acute need to focus on enhancing the level of professional commitment, life satisfaction and reducing the level of role conflict among female teacher educators by organising seminars, workshops and counselling sessions for them. Agarwal & Agarwal (2012) found total role conflict of male & female teachers is significantly related with their frustration tolerance. Harun (1997) conducted the study and found that role conflict varies significantly with age, size

of school, school authority, goals, superior and peer support, network of communication and teachers' role. Demographic factors: age and size of school, while organizational practices: school authority and network of communication were the major factors for role conflict. Roa and Ramasundaram (2008) revealed that married women were subjected to more role conflict than unmarried/single women. Jena (2011) found no significant difference in role conflict and work motivation among secondary school male and female tribal and also found no significant relationship between the role conflict and work motivation among secondary school male and female tribal.

Emotional intelligence is considered to involve emotional empathy, attention to, and discrimination of one's emotions, accurate recognition of one's own and other moods management or control over emotion, response with appropriate emotions and behaviors' in various life situations; and balancing of honest expression of emotions against courtesy, consideration, and respect. Emotional intelligence consists of five major parts i.e. knowing our own emotions, managing our own emotions, motivating ourselves, recognizing and influencing other's emotion and handling relationships (Goleman, 1995).

In the recent years, the concept of the emotional intelligence among teachers has been taken attention in the educational institutions due to its great importance. In fact, emotional intelligence is a type of intelligence that includes to control own and others emotions; make a choice between them and the ability of using these emotions to set the life. Therefore this skill is really required to make the teachers performance very effective. This skill can make the teachers not only able to deal with their students but with their colleagues as well. The ability to deal with the emotional upsets is powerful asset on the part of the teacher in building and maintaining the self-confidence. Hence, feelings and emotions are equally important in teaching learning process. When teacher is in the class, he/her must understand his/her own emotions of pupils and act appropriately. By virtue of this the teaching learning process can become enjoyable and productive. Bala (2017) revealed that the group of secondary school teachers with high emotional intelligence is more effective than the group of teachers with average or low emotional intelligence. There exists positive and significant relationship between teacher effectiveness and emotional intelligence among secondary school teachers. Bhardwa & Bhatt (2017) found that emotional intelligence is significantly related to the stress and life satisfaction of the secondary school teachers. It is concluded therefore that affective domain should be focused in teacher education programme/course instead of giving importance to only cognitive and psychomotor aspects for providing teacher training. Anjum & Swathi (2017) found that teachers with low emotional intelligence have poor quality of life and the teachers with high emotional intelligence have high quality of life. The results also show a positive correlation between emotional intelligence and quality of life. Aravpelli & Pasaragonda (2015) revealed that the private School teachers have fairly high level of Emotional Intelligence.

EMERGENCE OF THE PROBLEM

The present study finds the impact of emotional intelligence on Role conflict of teachers. Teachers are legally required by state constrictions to fill the role of educator in order to provide an equal learning opportunity for all children regardless of the differences in the student learning capabilities. Teachers are the facilitators of the learning experience by teaching student how to manage their time and problem solve difficult situations. Teacher are the model, what they imbibe get multiplied directly in the subsequent generations. The people who in educational institutions, especially for teacher or instructor working for colleges or universities faced many problems for managed their work and home. However, the contrast, feelings unhappy and not being willing to work, is also possible and even more. Common when many

teachers or instructors feel depressed in their workplaces due to some reasons, like role conflict, which affect their emotional intelligence and will for negatively.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

STUDY OF ROLE CONFLICT AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The study was delimited to 100 government and 100 private secondary school teachers of Amritsar district only.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS OF THE TERMS USED

ROLE CONFLICT

Role conflict is essentially a discrepancy between differing expectations of a role. If two people have different expectations for what the other's proper role should be, then role conflict is likely to ensure. Role conflict comes from the way we see each other on a daily basis and what role conflict we assign to one another within the conflict of work, family, life and interpersonal relationships. People often suffer from Role conflict, not just when they try to overcome their own biases and prejudices regarding what certain types of people can do or not do.

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

Emotional intelligence is the capacity for recognizing our own feelings and those for motivating ourselves and for managing emotions well in us and in our relationships.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the difference in role conflict of government and private secondary school teachers.
2. To study the difference in emotional intelligence of government and private secondary school teachers.
3. To study the difference in role conflict of male and female secondary school teachers.
4. To study the difference in emotional intelligence of male and female secondary school teachers.
5. To study the relationship of role conflict with emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. There exists no significant difference in role conflict of government and private secondary school teachers.
2. There exists no significant difference in emotional intelligence of government and private secondary school teachers.
3. There exists no significant difference in role conflict of male and female secondary school teachers.
4. There exists no significant difference in emotional intelligence of male and female secondary school teachers
5. There exists no relationship between role conflict and emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers.

METHOD AND PROCEDURE

DESIGN OF THE STUDY

The present study falls under the domain of descriptive research as it intends to study role conflict and emotional intelligence among secondary school teachers.

SAMPLE USED

A sample of about 100 male and 100 female secondary school teachers were randomly selected from government and private school affiliated to PSEB board Amritsar district.

The school wise and gender wise break up of this sample is being presented in table

Name of the Schools	Number of Male Teachers	Number of Female Teachers	Total
GOVERNMENT SCHOOLS			
Government Girls Senior Secondary School, Shivala Road	12	10	22
Government Girls Senior Secondary School, Mall Road	8	12	20
Government Senior Secondary School, Karampura	18	13	31
Government Girls Senior Secondary School, Chheharta	12	15	27
PRIVATE SCHOOLS			
Udham Singh Senior Secondary Schools, Putlighar, Amritsar	11	11	22
Jagat Jyoti Senior Secondary School, Putlighar, Amritsar	9	10	19
Khalsa College Girls Senior Secondary School, Amritsar	15	14	29
Khalsa College Boys Senior Secondary School, Amritsar	15	15	30
Total	100	100	200

TOOLS USED

- Teacher's Role Conflict Inventory (Prasad & Bhushan; 1991)
- Teacher's Emotional Intelligence Inventory (Mangal, 2008)

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

HYPOTHESIS 1

“There exists no significant difference in role conflict of government and private secondary school teachers”

In order to test this hypothesis, mean and S.D of Role conflict of government and private secondary school teachers was calculated. The scores of government and private secondary school teachers have been described in terms of mean, S.D and t-value in the table.

Table 1: Mean, S.D and t-value of role conflict of government and private secondary school teachers.

Role conflict	N	Mean	S.D	Std. Error Difference	df	't' Value
Government secondary school teachers	100	30.63	9.18	4.67	198	0.07
Private Secondary school teachers	100	31.23	9.22			

(Critical value 1.96 at 0.05 level and 2.58 at 0.01 level, df=198)

The table 1 revealed that the mean scores and S.D of government secondary school teachers is 30.63 and 9.18 respectively and mean scores and S.D of private secondary school teachers is 31.23 and 9.22 respectively. The t-value comes out to be 0.07 which is insignificant at both 0.01 and 0.05 level of

significance. Hence, the hypothesis no.1, “There exists no significant difference in role conflict of government and private secondary school teachers” is not rejected.

HYPOTHESIS 2

“There exists no significant difference in emotional intelligence of government and private secondary school teachers”

In order to test this hypothesis, mean and S.D of emotional intelligence of government and private secondary school teachers was calculated. The scores of government and private secondary school teachers have been described in terms of mean, S.D and t-value in the table.

Table 2: Mean, S.D and t-value of emotional intelligence of government and private secondary school teachers.

Emotional Intelligence	N	Mean	S.D	Std. Error Difference	df	‘t’ value
Government secondary school teachers	100	62.24	61.68	0.52	198	0.01
Private Secondary school teachers	100	63.31	11.09			

(Critical value 1.96 at 0.05 level and 2.58 at 0.01 level, df=198)

The table 2 revealed that the mean scores and S.D of government secondary school teachers is 62.24 and 61.68 respectively and mean scores and S.D of private secondary school teachers is 63.31 and 11.09 respectively. The t-value comes out to be 0.01 which is insignificant at both 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis no. 2, “There exists no significant difference in emotional intelligence of government and private secondary school teachers” is not rejected.

HYPOTHESIS 3

“There exists no significant difference in role conflict of male and female secondary school teachers”

In order to test this hypothesis, mean and S.D of role conflict of male and female secondary school teachers was calculated. The scores of male and female secondary school teachers have been described in terms of mean, S.D and t-value in the table.

Table 3: Mean, S.D and t-value of significance in role conflict of male and female secondary school teachers.

Gender	N	Mean	S.D	Std. Error Difference	df	‘t’ value
Male secondary school teachers	100	31.93	8.14	1.28	198	1.33
Female Secondary school teachers	100	30.23	9.92			

(Critical value 1.96 at 0.05 level and 2.58 at 0.01 level, df=198)

The table 3 revealed that the mean scores and S.D of male secondary school teachers is 31.93 and 8.14 respectively and mean scores and S.D of female secondary school teachers is 30.23 and 9.92 respectively. The t-value comes out to be 1.33 which is insignificant at both 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis no.3, “There exists no significant difference in role conflict of male and female secondary school teachers” is not rejected. The above result is supported by Dixon& Bruening (2007) who found that there is no significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers in role conflict.

HYPOTHESIS 4

“There exists no significant difference in emotional intelligence of male and female secondary school teachers”

In order to test this hypothesis, mean and S.D of emotional intelligence of male and female secondary school

teachers was calculated. The scores of male and female secondary school teachers have been described in terms of mean, S.D and t-value in the table.

Table 4: Mean, S.D and t-value of significance in emotional intelligence of male and female secondary school teachers

Gender	N	Mean	S.D	Std. Error Difference	df	't' value
Male secondary school teachers	100	63.30	9.35	1.45	198	0.75
Female Secondary school teachers	100	62.21	11.14			

(Critical value 1.96 at 0.05 level and 2.58 at 0.01 level, df=198)

The table 4 revealed that the mean scores and S.D of male secondary school teachers is 63.30 and 9.35 respectively and mean scores and S.D of female secondary school teachers is 62.21 and 11.14 respectively. The t-value comes out to be 0.75 which is insignificant at both 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis no.4, "There exists no significant difference in emotional intelligence of male and female secondary school teachers" is not rejected. The above result is supported by Sreeja (2005) who found that there is no significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers in emotional intelligence.

HYPOTHESIS 5

"There exists no relationship between role conflict and emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers"

In order to test this hypothesis, coefficient of correlation of role conflict and emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers was calculated. The scores of coefficient of correlation of role conflict and emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers have been show in the table.

Table 5: Coefficient of correlation of role conflict and emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers

Variable	Role conflict	Emotional Intelligence
Role conflict		0.04
Emotional Intelligence	0.04	

The table 5 reveals that the role conflict and emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers have positive but weak correlation hence, the hypothesis no.5, "There exists no relationship between role conflict and emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers" is not rejected.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

- There exists no significant difference in role conflict of government and private secondary school teachers.
- There exists no significant difference in emotional intelligence of government and private secondary school teachers.
- There exists no significant difference in role conflict of male and female secondary school teachers.
- There exists no significant difference in emotional intelligence of male and female secondary school teachers
- There exists no relationship between role conflict and emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATION

- From the findings it is reported that there exists no significant difference in role conflict of government and private secondary school teachers. All the government and private teachers need to be empowered by giving autonomy. Therefore it is necessary to identify the teachers, drives and needs and to channelize their behavior to motivate towards task performance.
- The present study provide enormous scope for the improvement of teachers' job satisfaction and work motivation through well-structured sensitization, attitude building and competency based training programs.
- Training workshops are suggested to be held for teachers to develop their understanding of important component of teaching –learning process.

SUGGESTIONS

- The research on the variables of role conflict and emotional intelligence may be conducted on teachers teaching at primary level and college as well.
- A comparative study may be conducted on the variables of role conflict and emotional intelligence of pre-service and in service teachers.
- The present study was conducted on the sample of Government and Private secondary school teachers. The similar study may be conduct on the other institutions or colleges like Medical colleges, engineering colleges etc.

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